

Human activity modelling and recognition for collaborative robotics based on hand-object interaction

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Abstract—With the future advent of Industry 5.0 it is necessary to develop and enhance collaborative robotics, introduced within the Industry 4.0 paradigm. This entails establishing a new paradigm to handle the communication and interaction between the actors of the workcell. Collaboration is then improved, making it more fluent, reliable, and able to correct workers' oversights. To this end, this paper introduces a new architecture that combines the reliability of PLC logic with the scalability of predicates tailored to a specific process. Such logic and predicates are masked to the operator through an interface that intervenes only when errors have to be notified. After giving a semantic meaning to each object of the workstation, the proposed architecture supervises the worker during the whole operation, modelling errors and recovering from them.

Index Terms—Human-Robot Collaboration; Human-Machine Interfaces; Intelligent and Flexible Manufacturing;

I. INTRODUCTION

Future manufacturing paradigms will require flexibility and cognitive capabilities to respond to the increasing needs of mass customisation. Production environments will be then populated by humans and robots, sharing the same workspace [1]. Collaborative robots need to be endowed with advanced perception and reasoning capabilities, in order to understand what their human fellow co-workers are doing, [2], or about to do [3]. In this framework, the major challenge is to build computational models to semantically interpret human behaviour. Activity recognition [4] is of paramount importance to allow the robotic counterpart to select the most appropriate behaviour, even anticipating the human [5]. Recognition based on interaction with objects is particularly relevant in this context. Although interfaces between humans and robots have been the subject of several studies in the literature, industrial applications are still far from being transparent to the users. The present work contributes in the integration of human-robot collaboration, introducing a new, non invasive, paradigm to model the workflow, making it more reliable and less error prone. This is obtained thanks to the combination of a PLC-like logic and predicates composed by a series of signals that can be customized depending on the sensors available in the workcell. The proposed solution grants immediate error detection and correction by the smart supervisor [6], increas-

ing human-robot synchronization and ensuring a more fluent collaboration. A method to model human-object interaction is also introduced with the aim of recognising human activities along with the current advancement of manual activities.

II. ARCHITECTURE FOR HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION

In the following, a control architecture, allowing to model the desired execution of a collaborative task, is formally introduced. The proposed architecture is sketched in Fig. 1 and accounts for three major components:

- 1) the block *World model* contains a digital representation of the work-space [7].
- 2) the block *Boolean expression(s)* simply allows to specify a set of Boolean expressions to be evaluated during the execution of the program;
- 3) the block *Control logic* contains all programmed logic needed for the execution of the collaborative application.

The *World model* contains digital representations of all the relevant entities (workers, robots, objects, etc.) in the workspace. The state of each digital twin is continuously updated through measurements coming from the field, in the form of ETHERNET messages (e.g. to update the position/velocity of each robot) or through a surveillance sensor (e.g. to locate objects and/or humans). The state of the *World model* is accessible via *Closed predicates*, which are queries on its internal state. The results of the evaluated *Closed predicates* are stored, in the form of Boolean values, in a *Signal register*, together with physical signals coming directly from the field. These are then combined in the *Boolean expression* block and their results are passed to the *Control logic*, specified through a SFC program. It models the task and sends commands to the robot, supervising the operator.

III. ACTIVITY RECOGNITION STRATEGY

To develop a possible *Closed predicate* to infer whether or not the worker is currently performing an activity, it is fundamental to understand whether an object is being manipulated by the human, and in which position this manipulation happens. We classify an activity as the action of manipulating a tool (object), which is further specified by the position in the

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed architecture for the development of human-robot collaborative applications.

Fig. 2. Modelling of the hand-object interaction: interaction seen from the sensor, and automaton \mathcal{A} to model the hand-object interaction.

work-space where this activity is taking place. For the purpose of activity recognition, the object has to be detected and its position $\mathbf{p}_O \in \mathbb{R}^3$ has to be compared with the position of the hand of the worker $\mathbf{p}_H \in \mathbb{R}^3$. Both the positions of the object and of the worker's hand are assumed to be tracked with state-of-the-art methods. If the object is sufficiently far from the hand, i.e. $\|\mathbf{p}_O - \mathbf{p}_H\| > t$, $t > 0$ being a threshold, it is surely not being manipulated by the human. The same applies if the object is not detected at all. In turn, if the distance between \mathbf{p}_O and \mathbf{p}_H drops below the given threshold, it is likely that the human is using the object to perform some manipulation. The hand-object interaction strategy is modelled by means of the automaton \mathcal{A} (Fig. 2). Based on the state of the automaton and on the position of the hand in the work-space, it is then possible to infer the action that is taking place in that particular moment in the work-space, as, in an industrial setting, the intrinsic semantic meaning of an object is known a priori. In the light of the above, the elements that are needed to correctly infer the current action are: the knowledge of which object is in use, the position of operator's hands and the creation of a predicate that evaluates these two pieces of information. A predicate can be a combination of whatever signals, being it deduced by the supervision system or physically triggered. From the combination of several predicates we are then able to verify that a particular action in a specific place is happening. In this framework, the integration of the predicates with the SFC logic comes very useful since the supervisor can trigger

the next operation only if the correct action is performed in that right moment, otherwise an error is notified.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The use-case consists in a human-robot collaborative assembly of the rear braking system of a motorbike. The scene is monitored by a surveillance camera which embeds human and object tracking capabilities. Two volumes V1 and V2 are identified in the work-space. V1 is used to start the operation: the robot starts moving only when the volume is considered occupied. On the other side, V2 corresponds to the place where the operator should perform the tightening operations: the supervisor continuously checks if the operator's hands are inside this volume holding the appropriate tool. The working progresses have been modelled with the SFC program divided in two parts that track, respectively, the human activities and the robot. Thanks to the usage of tailored predicates for the particular operation, the supervising system is able to spot and correct errors. The accompanying video shows the complete experiment.

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